

Catalytic Properties of Oxides of Lanthanum, Neodymium and Samarium obtained by Solid State Decomposition of Oxalates. Part-III.

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The catalytic and electrical properties of non-stoichiometric oxides of La, Nd and Sm have been studied. Oxide samples from samarium oxalate do not show catalytic activity for the decomposition of H_2O_2 . Electrical conductivity has also been measured. A simple relation between catalytic property and conductivity has been observed

WE have been engaged¹⁻³ in developing non-stoichiometric oxides of inner transition metals in an attempt to correlate the catalytic activity with that of solid state properties. It has been observed that the non-stoichiometric oxides of La, Nd and Sm, obtained from solid state decomposition of their nitrates, are quite active for the decomposition of H_2O_2 . These oxides are insulators and the electrical conductivity has been discussed in terms of small polarons. The present paper deals with the study of the catalytic and electrical properties of non-stoichiometric oxides of La, Nd and Sm, obtained from their oxalates. The oxide samples of Sm seem to possess no activity for the decomposition of H_2O_2 . A linear relationship between activity and conductivity has been observed.

Experimental

Oxalates of La, Nd and Sm (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and H_2O_2 (G.R., Sarabhai) were used as such.

The samples were prepared by following the reported method⁴. The decomposition of H_2O_2 was studied as reported earlier⁴. The reaction was studied in acidic medium (pH 4.5) at three different temperatures, i.e. 30, 40 and 50°. The metals in oxides were estimated according to the reported procedure² and empirical formulae derived (Table 1).

Electrical conductivity: Powdered specimens were pelletised into disc (1.29 cm dia $\times$ 0.10–0.20 cm) at uniform pressure of 8 tons/inch². The electrical conductivity of the sample was determined following the previous procedure².

Results and Discussion

The decomposition of H_2O_2 on La-oxide sample is kinetically of the first order (Fig. 1) and that on Nd-oxide samples follows the same pattern. The rate constants calculated from the initial slopes of the rate curves, energy of activation and frequency

TABLE I - KINETIC DATA FOR DECOMPOSITION OF 0.5% H_2O_2 IN PRESENCE OF OXIDE SAMPLES

Sample from	Decomp. temp. °C	Empirical formula	Specific rate ($\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at			E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	log 10A	E_g (eV)
			30°	40°	50°			
La-oxalate	600	LaO _{1.90}	*	*	*	—	—	—
	700	LaO _{1.80}	0.133	0.575	1.644	26.20	19.00	1.13
	800	LaO _{1.98}	1.000	1.700	4.600	14.27	10.27	1.35
	960	LaO _{0.04}	0.276	0.506	1.278	16.90	12.57	1.28
Nd-oxalate	607	NdO _{1.68}	—	—	—	—	—	—
	700	NdO _{0.86}	0.057	0.140	0.456	20.19	14.75	1.09
	800	NdO _{0.06}	0.200	0.426	1.150	16.68	12.37	0.91
	960	NdO _{0.88}	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sm-oxalate	600	SmO _{1.66}	*	*	*	—	—	—
	700	SmO _{1.86}	*	*	*	—	—	—
	800	SmO _{0.84}	*	*	*	—	—	—
	960	SmO _{0.18}	*	*	*	—	—	—

*Inactive.

Fig 1 1st order plot for decomposition of H_2O_2 on La-oxide samples at : (O) 50° , (Δ) 40° and (x) 30° C.

factors (Table 1) reveal the following points : (i) the La-oxide sample obtained at 600° and Nd-oxide samples obtained at 600° and 960° from the oxalates are found to be inactive for the decomposition of H_2O_2 , (ii) all the Sm-oxide samples obtained from Sm-oxalate are catalytically inactive for decomposing H_2O_2 , (iii) the La-oxide sample prepared at 800° shows greater activity than the other oxides, and (iv) the catalytic activity of the oxide samples decreases with the increase in atomic number of the lanthanide ; the same sequence in reactivity has also been observed in the case of the oxide samples obtained from nitrate¹. Thus oxides of La, Nd and Sm from different origins show different activity for decomposing H_2O_2 . Further, oxide samples of La, Nd and Sm obtained from the oxalates are of less catalytic potentialities in comparison to their nitrate counterparts, though their method of preparation is the same.

The compositions of the different oxide samples are given in Table 1. All oxide samples are non-stoichiometric. Results on the composition of the samples show that deviation from stoichiometry in the direction of oxygen content bears no simple relation with the rise in decomposition temperature. At first it seems probable to attribute the cause of catalytic activity to the degree of non-stoichiometry which the oxide sample attains. However oxides with comparable degree of non-stoichiometry from Sm-oxalate donot show catalytic activity for the

decomposition of H_2O_2 , in obvious contrast to the oxides from La and Nd which are found to be active. Some major changes in their structures with respect to metal and oxygen atoms rendering these samples inactive for the decomposition process, seem probable. However, in spite of painstaking attempts undertaken, this could not be confirmed owing to the failure in determining the crystal structure of the inactive samples on account of

FIG 2 DECOMPOSITION OF H_2O_2 IN DIFFERENT MEDIUM (O) La OXIDE FROM OXALATE AT 800° AND (●) NEODYMIUM OXIDE FROM OXALATE AT 800°

polycrystalline nature of the samples as well as experimental limitations.

Fig. 1 shows the non-linearity downwards indicating these oxides to be more active in the initial stage of the reaction. Fig. 2 presents the variation of rate constant of the decomposition of H_2O_2 with that of pH values of the medium. It is clear, that the rate constant decreases with the increase in pH value and becomes lowest at pH=7.0 and then increases. Similar observation was recorded in the earlier investigation¹. Further, the method of competing reactions^{5,6} was employed to detect the radical chain processes, if any. These results support the views on the mechanism of decomposition of H_2O_2 expressed by earlier workers¹. In the light of the present findings obtained for the elucidation of mechanism of decomposition of H_2O_2 , it is obvious that the same mechanistic pathways as evolved by earlier investigators, seem to be operative. However, the downward hump observed (Fig. 1) in the initial stage of the curve indicates the striking difference in the kinetic behaviours between the oxide samples obtained from the oxalates and that from the nitrates, which shows the induction period in the decomposition process.

It was thought that the undecomposed part of the oxalate present in the oxide sample might have made the Sm-oxide samples inactive. Accordingly, the usual titration method was followed to determine the undecomposed oxalates. The Sm-oxide samples prepared at 600, 700 and 800° contain 1.88, 0.70 and 0.23% undecomposed oxalate respectively. The presence of oxalate ions might deactivate these samples for the decomposition process. But it is interesting to point out that the Sm-oxide sample obtained at 960° does not show catalytic activity though it contains no oxalate ions.

Electrical properties: The plots of electrical conductivity as a function of temperature in the range of 373–873 K for Sm-oxide samples are shown in Fig. 3. Similar trends are obtained in case of oxide samples of La and Nd (Fig. 4). The plots reveal that above 633 K, the conductivity increases with the increase in temperature showing semiconducting behaviour. The conductivity remains unchanged in the temperature range 373–633 K. The conductivity data in the temperature range 633–923 K can be expressed by the relation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_g/2KT) \quad (1)$$

The mechanism for electrical conduction of these oxide solid has been explained using band theory¹. Electrical conduction in the solid has been attributed to the creation of small or intermediate polarons by the electron in the conduction band. Further, the charge transport excitation of electron from the valence band is estimated to be of the order of 3 eV at normal temperature. Thus, the oxide samples are good insulator. On account of strong interaction of trapped electrons with cation

the conductivity does not change with increase of temperature in this range.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ of samarium oxides from oxalates at : (○) 600°, (●) 700°, (□) 800° and (×) 960°C.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ of La-oxide at : (○) 700°, (△) 800° and (□) 900°; and Nd-oxide at : (×) 700° and (⊙) 800°C.

Rate constant and electrical conductivity : Table 1 contains the value of energy of activation (E_g) for conductance for the samples found catalytically active. The analysis of the electrical transport and catalytic activity data led to some possible relationship between the energy of activation (E_g) for conductance and the energy of activation (E_a) for the decomposition processes. We may conclude that for the same oxide E_g and E_a bears reciprocal relationship. Most of the oxide samples obtained from oxalates seem to be catalytically inactive

Fig. 5. Plots of E_g for conductance vs E_a for decomposition: oxides from (●) Sm-carbonate and (△) Nd-carbonate.

(Table 1). We fail to arrive at a convincing conclusion of the possible relationship between E_g and E_a . On account of this difficulty, we prepared oxide samples from carbonates which are found catalytically active (Fig. 5). It indicates the variation of E_g with E_a for different oxide samples. Now it is to be concluded that E_g for conductance varies linearly with E_a for decomposition processes. The similar linear relationship has also been observed by Poddar⁷, who studied the decomposition of H_2O_2 on the oxide samples of Ce and Pr. The relationship reflects the view that the species which are responsible for catalytic activity also act as a charge carriers or sites for electron transfer. However, more work is needed to corroborate the above conclusions. The same conclusion is also reflected from variation of energy gap of activation for conduction with rate constant for decomposition of H_2O_2 . However further work is underway to test the validity of the above conclusion.

Conclusions : Activity of the oxide samples decreases with rise in the atomic number of the elements. Samarium oxide obtained from oxalate do not show catalytic activity. There appears a simple relation between electrical conductivity and rate constant.

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References

1. J. N. TIWARI and S. BHAGAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 438.
2. M. SAHA, R. KUMAR and S. BHAGAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 384.
3. R. KUMAR, J. N. TIWARI and S. BHAGAT, *Fertilizer Tech* in the press
4. S. BHAGAT and L. D. AUJHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 358.
5. L. A. NIKOLAEV, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1958, 32, 1131.
6. J. KRALJIC and C. N. TRUMBOR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 87, 2547.
7. P. PODDAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Bhagalpur University, 1987.